

CASE REPORT **OPEN ACCESS**

Mental Health Prevalence Determinants and Strategies for Well-Being

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Abstract

Mental health is a fundamental component of overall well-being, yet it remains one of the most neglected aspects of health globally. The present study reviews the prevalence, risk factors, and strategies for mental health promotion. Global data suggest that mental health disorders are increasing due to urbanization, stress, and social isolation. Early diagnosis, effective treatment, and preventive interventions can significantly improve individual and community health outcomes.

Introduction

Mental health is a fundamental component of overall health and well-being, influencing how individuals think, feel, and interact with others in society. It determines the capacity to handle stress, make informed decisions, and maintain productive social and professional relationships [1]. Unlike physical health, mental health often remains overlooked despite its profound impact on quality of life and global productivity.

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), one in eight people worldwide suffer from some form of mental disorder, with depression and anxiety being the most prevalent [2]. These conditions contribute significantly to the global burden of disease, accounting for substantial disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) and economic losses [3]. Mental health disorders are influenced by a wide range of determinants, including biological (genetics, petrochemical imbalances), psychological (trauma, personality traits), and social factors (poverty, stigma, social isolation) [4,5].

In recent years, rapid urbanization, lifestyle changes, and the psychosocial impact of global crises, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, have exacerbated the prevalence of mental health issues [6]. Despite growing awareness, many individuals lack access to appropriate mental health services due to stigma, insufficient healthcare infrastructure, and limited policy implementation [7].

Addressing mental health challenges requires a multifaceted approach that combines early diagnosis, evidence-based interventions such as cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) and mindfulness, and the integration of mental health into primary care systems. Furthermore, community-based awareness programs and lifestyle modifications-including regular exercise, adequate sleep, and stress management-play a pivotal role in promoting well-being

This article aims to explore the prevalence, determinants, and strategies for improving mental health, emphasizing the urgent need for comprehensive interventions to enhance individual and societal outcomes.

Methodology

A narrative review was conducted to explore the prevalence, determinants, and strategies for mental health promotion. Relevant literature was retrieved from PubMed, Scopus, and World Health Organization (WHO) databases covering the period 2015 to 2024. The keywords used for the search included mental health, depression, anxiety, stress, and mental well-being. Inclusion criteria comprised studies and reports that focused on global prevalence, risk determinants, and evidence-based interventions related to mental health. Exclusion criteria included studies that were

purely pharmacological or lacked relevance to mental health outcomes in community or public health contexts. The selected studies were analyzed qualitatively to synthesize key findings for this review.

Results

The analysis revealed that mental health disorders remain a major global health concern, affecting approximately 970 million individuals worldwide [5]. Among these, depression impacts 280 million people, while anxiety disorders affect 301 million individuals, making them the most common psychiatric conditions [6]. Collectively, these disorders are recognized as leading contributors to disability-adjusted life years (DALYs), imposing a substantial health and economic burden globally [7]. The determinants of poor mental health were found to be multifactorial, encompassing biological, psychological, and social factors. Biological determinants include genetic predisposition, hormonal imbalances, and neurological conditions, whereas psychological determinants involve personality traits, past trauma, and chronic stress. Additionally, social determinants such as poverty, unemployment, discrimination, and social isolation significantly exacerbate the risk of mental health disorders [9]. In response to these findings, several strategies for mental health promotion were identified. Early diagnosis and treatment remain the cornerstone, with cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT) and pharmacotherapy proving highly effective. Community-based approaches, including support groups, helplines, and counseling services, play a critical role in reducing stigma and facilitating care. Moreover, lifestyle modifications, such as regular exercise, adequate sleep, and mindfulness practices, enhance overall mental well-being. At the policy level, integrating mental health services into primary healthcare systems and implementing nationwide anti-stigma campaigns are essential to improve accessibility and long-term outcomes.

Discussion

This review highlights that mental health disorders are on the rise globally; with a disproportionate impact on low- and middle-income countries where healthcare resources and mental health services remain limited [5]. Despite the increasing prevalence, social stigma continues to act as a major barrier to early diagnosis and effective treatment, preventing many individuals from seeking timely care. Evidence-based interventions, including cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT), mindfulness practices, and community-based programs, have demonstrated significant effectiveness in reducing the burden of mental health disorders and improving patient outcomes. Furthermore, the integration of mental health services into primary healthcare systems can facilitate early detection, reduce disability-adjusted life years (DALYs), and promote holistic health care delivery. A multidimensional approach, combining clinical interventions, social support, and policy-driven initiatives, is therefore crucial to address the growing mental health crisis.

Conclusion

Mental health is an essential component of overall well-being. Governments, healthcare providers, and communities must prioritize mental health by improving awareness, accessibility, and integrating preventive strategies into public health programs.

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